

STUDYING THE OPERA "DILAROM" BY MUKHTAR ASHRAFI IN MUSICAL CULTURE LESSONS IN A COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOL

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The opera "Dilaram" by Mukhtar Ashrafi was written based on the poem "Seven Planets" by L. Navoi (librettists K. Yashen, M. Mukhamedov). In Navoi's poem "Seven Planets" Shah Bahram is so carried away by the slave ("cunning idol") Dilaram that he takes her with him hunting - the favorite pastime of the Iranian nobility. But in a fit of rage caused by the mocking attitude to his shooting skills, the Shah banishes Dilaram to the desert. Seven fairy tale poems, told by travelers to entertain the bored Shah, are skillfully woven into this plot. The author's idea runs through the entire narrative: a ruler who neglects the affairs of the state, the well-being of his subjects for the sake of hunting, amusements and love affairs is worthy of condemnation. Spending his days hunting and his nights at feasts, Shah Bahram:

Left the whole kingdom unattended,
The whole state fell into disarray.
The Shah departed from just deeds,
Whoever had pleasure, did what he wanted.

At the end of the poem, Navoi passes a harsh sentence on the Shah; the powerful ruler of the Sassanid state with his brilliant retinue drowns in a disgusting mess of swamp mud and the blood of slaughtered animals.

In the opera, the "balance of power" is completely different. The slave Dilaram is the personification of purity and nobility. She and the artist Moni love each other, and Shah Bahram, who bought the beautiful harpist and imprisoned Moni, ruins the happiness of the lovers. Despite the common names of the main characters, and the coincidence of individual moments of the plot, the plot of the libretto "Dilaram" has little in common with the poem "Seven Planets". Of course, turning to classical examples of literature, the creators of the opera have the right to interpret them in their own way.

The rich melody of the opera captivates. For the most part, it is borrowed from the field of developed forms of Uzbek professional music of the oral tradition. The main characters are characterized with the help of beautiful examples of the Uzbek national heritage. Genuine folk melodies - Tajik, Iranian, Indian, Arabic - are successfully used in the divertissement scenes of the opera. An important role in the characterization of the artist Moni is

played by the ancient melody "Karimkul-begi". It forms the basis of Moni's large aria in the dramatic finale of the first act (Dilaram is sold to the shah, Moni vows to find his beloved. Accompanying Moni's subsequent appearances, the melody "Karimkul-begi" acquires the meaning of the hero's leitmotif. Another aria (the beginning of the second act), in which Moni tells the sage Nugman about his misadventures, is built on the melody "Sarakhbori-navo" from the maqom "Navo". The music associated with the further fate of Moni retains its contemplative character, only its emotional structure becomes increasingly mournful. This is natural, since it reflects the stage behavior of the hero; the suffering of Moni, imprisoned in the dungeon of the palace (the beginning of the third act), his farewell to the dying Dilaram (the final scene of the opera).

The same sphere of emotions is characteristic of the musical part of the main heroine. This is evidenced by many local statements of Dilaram: her aria "The soul is burning..." (the first scene) - dreams of happiness with a loved one, the romance "Zhonim mening" - "My soul" (the second scene), music expressing the sadness of Dilaram, languishing in the chambers of Bahram (the fourth scene); her sad song about broken love, emphasizing the contrast between the sad fate of the unfortunate slave and the magnificent luxury, the fun of the royal feast (the sixth scene). Very beautiful and scenically effective are the vocalizations of Dilaram, who unexpectedly appears in the midst of the clash between the peasants and the warriors of Bahram (the third scene). Enchanted by the unusual beauty of the harpist's voice, the warriors lower their weapons. Everyone froze, conquered by the mighty power of the music. Dilaram's vocalizations turn into a song. The intonations of augmented seconds, typical of Iranian music, give this song a unique flavor, and make it stand out in the generally very diatonic part of the main character. The part of Nugman, a fair and wise vizier, is written in the same vein as the parts of the main characters. Its melodic basis is also the song genres of the traditional heritage. Such, for example, is the aria-reflection of Nugman, sympathizing with the suffering of the poor prisoners (the fifth scene), which arose on the basis of the melody of the folk song "Ulturgisi" ("Sit with me"). The commonality of musical means characterizing Dilaram, Moni and Nugmon is quite justified, since both the lovers and the noble vizier are representatives of the progressive camp. The main "bearer of evil" - Shah Bahram - receives the characteristics of a leitmotif type. But rather neutral music is not able to convey the typical features of a cruel and

formidable shah. Bahram's vocal part is intonationally close to the parts of positive heroes.

In many scenes of the opera, Shah Bahram appears surrounded by his magnificent retinue. The basis of the courtiers' chorus (third scene) is one of the variants of a melody widespread in Central Asia and Iran. But the means of artistic influence of this folk melody are clearly insufficient to depict the world of violence and evil.

The absence of clear musical characteristics of the opposing forces, as well as some static nature of the musical images, negatively affects the musical dramaturgy of the opera. This is especially clearly manifested in the finale of the opera, where the tragic denouement of the story of the unfortunate lovers is more vividly embodied on stage than in music.

Many fragments of the opera are attractive in a purely musical sense. These include the arias of lovers and the song of Dilaram with a choir of girls in the first scene, the colorful scene "Bazaar" (beginning of the second act), in which the choir and orchestra, complementing each other, create a vivid picture of a noisy, crowded oriental bazaar. The dances in the Shah's palace (beginning of the fourth act), where expressive melodies of different oriental peoples sound in a rich colorful design, are spectacular. These memorable musical episodes, as well as the talented performance of the main characters' parts, determined the success of "Dilaram" among a wide audience. Not the least important role here was played by the splendor and entertainment of the spectacular side of the performance (rich staging, luxurious design and costumes), as well as the magnificent dances staged by G. Izmailova.

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